

Considerations for Implementing Electronic Laboratory Notebooks in an Academic Research Environment

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Abstract

As research becomes predominantly digitalised, scientists have the option of using electronic laboratory notebooks to record and access entries, meeting volume, complexity, accessibility and preservation requirements where paper notebooks fall short. The technology can yield many benefits; however, these can only be realised by choosing a system that properly fulfils the requirements of a given context. This perspective explores the considerations for an academic focused electronic laboratory notebook by citing pertinent studies, as well as drawing from our own experience implementing a system within a multi-disciplinary research environment. We consider how the required financial and time investment is shared between individuals and institutions. Finally, we discuss how electronic laboratory notebooks fit into the broader context of research data management. This perspective is not a product review; it provides a framework for both the initial consideration of an electronic laboratory notebook and the evaluation of specific software packages.

Main

The past 20 years have seen a rapid increase in the number of Electronic Lab Notebook software packages

Electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs) have been mooted in various forms since the late 1950s.¹ In the 1980s, software such as RS/1 (Bolt, Beranek and Newman, Inc.) offered researchers the capability to store, analyse and comment upon data.^{2,3} ELNs are presented as a tool for improving the reproducibility of research by facilitating the transfer of vital experimental details, both between generations of researchers and across different research groups.^{4,5} Recording, accessing and preserving paper-based records can be slow, inefficient and difficult to integrate with modern computer-controlled data capture systems. However, implementing an ELN is non-trivial. Its adoption requires clear understanding of notebook use in a given laboratory setting, and the provision of sufficient resources.

The majority of current ELNs are commercial offerings. These offer access to proprietary software, typically hosted remotely and available via subscription, under a software as a service (SaaS) business model. A few community-developed open-source ELNs exist, with freely accessible codebases. There are also a small number of commercial ELNs with open-source codebases, and free (to non-profit organisations) ELNs with proprietary codebases. Reviewing specific products is beyond the scope of this perspective, however, a number of product comparisons are available online.⁶⁻⁹

In the past twenty years, the number of ELNs has increased dramatically, as the benefits of digitisation have been recognised (**Figure 1**). In this marketplace not all ELNs have proven successful. A significant number of both commercially available and open-source software packages have ultimately become defunct. In our analysis of 171 ELN products (95 active, 76 defunct), the average lifetime of an ELN was found to be 7 (± 4.4) years (median \pm median absolute deviation). The lifetimes breakdown as 6 (± 5.1) years, $n = 24$, and 7 (± 4.4) years, $n = 147$ for open-source and proprietary codebases respectively. The longest running open-source ELN has been active for 20 years, and the longest running proprietary ELN for 25 years. Company acquisitions, changes in the commercial market and lack of developer support or funding for open-source projects, can all result in defunct ELNs. Long-term support and data access should be a primary concern when implementing an ELN: many benefits (for example, rapid access to historic notebook entries) disappear if archived material is trapped inside inaccessible legacy systems, or worse, deleted. Procedures for

extracting and archiving data in accessible formats should be part of any deployment strategy.

Figure 1: Timeline of 171 ELN software packages, documenting known or estimated release and cessation year. The area of the circles shown at the top of the figure is proportional to the number of new ELNs launched in a given year. Data is segregated into proprietary (blue) and open-source (pink) codebases, and sorted within these categories according to the number of years the software has been active. Insets are screenshots of a selection of ELNs, showing the progression of software development with time, including: RS/1 (Bolt Beranek and Newman Inc), reprinted (adapted) with permission from Borman et al.² Copyright (1985) American Chemical Society. Virtual Notebook System (Baylor College of Medicine), permission pending.¹⁰ ELOG (Paul Scherrer Institute), captured from online source.¹¹ eLabFTW (Deltablot),¹² captured from authors' own server. OSF (Centre for Open Science), captured from online source.¹³ See Supplementary Note 1 for a description of the survey methodology and limitations. This plot incorporates data from primary and secondary sources.^{8,14,15}

Before choosing an ELN, identify the purpose of the laboratory notebook

A laboratory notebook serves a variety of purposes. For the researcher it is a record of experiments or work conducted. The notebook may describe experimental methods, be a direct record of original data, or provide metadata required to contextualise other data. Formal metadata (experimental test parameters and control conditions) may be supplemented by unplanned observations and annotations, both facilitating data analysis and interpretation. A notebook may journal both idea genesis and the decision making process.¹⁶ Successfully capturing this information is critical to both the researcher and others attempting to replicate the work.

Laboratory notebooks can be used to enforce good practice or to standardise workflows. For example, institutions may mandate the inclusion of risk assessment templates within synthetic chemistry notebooks to encourage researchers to identify and mitigate hazards immediately prior to conducting a reaction. Routine procedures with well-defined outputs may follow a standard notebook template, to minimise repetition and standardise record keeping, or to record quality control procedures. An ELN can simplify this by acting as a database of templates and protocols.^{15,17} For researchers, managers and institutions, laboratory notebooks provide evidence of work completed, facilitating internal accountability, and providing a legal record to demonstrate regulatory compliance and potentially aiding intellectual property protection.

Identifying a given laboratory's requirements defines and constrains the choice of ELN. Academic research laboratories typically feature a diverse range of experiments, data types and disciplines, resulting in different perceptions of the same ELN package, depending on the user's background.¹⁸ While many ELNs are specialist products, targeting researchers in a specific domain (e.g. biochemistry or pharmacology), these may not be relevant or sufficiently flexible for most researchers, a limitation already recognised by the early creators of ELNs in the 1990s,¹⁹ and again in recent studies.¹⁵ Record keeping may be required to meet regulatory standards, for example for laboratories accredited to the testing and calibration standards ISO 17025:2017 and ISO 15189:2012,^{20,21} which stipulate requirements for laboratory information management, or for those wishing to adhere to general electronic record keeping standards such as the Code of Federal Regulations Title 21 Part.²²

ELNs recover researcher time and enable better research practices, in return for financial cost

ELNs provide quality-of-life improvements over paper notebooks, the greatest being the ease of locating and sharing information.²³ In environments where ELNs have been implemented, the ease with which information can be sought and shared is regarded as one of the key benefits.¹⁷ Exposing ELN entries to multiple users is often simple to accomplish within the software. Project teams can instantly access relevant experimental data across different researchers. Supervisors can remotely provide feedback without physical access to a notebook. Collaborators can be geographically separate, working in separate laboratories across multiple countries. Notebook entries can be archived in situ as team members leave, while allowing incoming students and staff instant access. The ability to rapidly search through all available content allows researchers to filter and access ELN entries pertinent to their own work.^{16,23}

Table 1 illustrates how the differences between interacting with paper and electronic laboratory notebooks are ultimately a choice between time and money. Paper notebooks can be an inexpensive medium but executing actions that are trivial with an ELN (searching,

sharing, data backup, etc.) are time expensive. Conversely, most ELNs are relatively expensive to implement and maintain, compared to paper notebooks, but provide far greater functionality at a much lower time cost to the researcher. When considering any ELN system the benefits of enabling more time to be dedicated to research, improving knowledge transfer and experimental reproducibility are balanced against financial costs. Recognising who will bear these costs is important. For example, relying upon users to provide their own computing device to access an ELN effectively transfers this cost onto the researcher. This may cause people to spurn ELN adoption and disadvantages researchers without existing devices, as seen in studies of undergraduate web-based learning technologies.^{24,25} If a laboratory already has a sufficient number of network connected workstations, then this cost may already be nil, or otherwise will form a significant proportion of the overall implementation cost (a factor not included in any software vendor pricing).

Interaction	Paper notebook	Electronic notebook
Searching through entries	Time consuming, reliant upon user constructed index	Fast, searchable by keyword, time, user, metadata tags, etc
Reordering entries	Impossible, limited to chronological order, challenging when multiple concurrent experiments	Dynamic, instantly able to sort and present entries according to metadata
Using templates, linking to common equipment/reagent information, or standard operating procedures (SOPs)	Printing and pasting documents into notebook, or reliant on written reference – time consuming and static	Templates, equipment/reagent details, or SOPs can be held in a central database and dynamically linked directly to one of more entries
Reading entries (intelligibility, accessibility)	Reliant on user to write clear, intelligible notes Limited accessibility	Standardises input as typewritten text Potential to improve accessibility using handwriting and/or voice recognition software
Embedding non-text computer generated content (e.g. digital photographs, screenshots, code snippets)	Requires printing, followed by pasting into notebook	Trivial; may be embedded in-line with text or attached as file
Embedding hand-drawn illustrations, equations, chemical structures	Trivial, can be drawn directly into notebook	May be challenging without appropriate hardware (e.g. a stylus) and compatible ELN. Some ELNs incorporate specialist equation/structure editors
Sharing notebook entries	Time intensive, involving scanning and sending relevant entries, or run risk of notebook loss	Trivial; a hierarchy of permissions can be established for a given entry Data access can be provided instantly, worldwide if required
Backing up notebooks	Time intensive to scan entire notebook	Trivial – data can automatically be copied to multiple locations on user-defined basis
Physically storing notebooks	Over time can amount to significant space requirements for larger laboratories	Institution-level storage possible on single server, with possibility to outsource storage to data centre

Accessing archived or historical entries	Time intensive	An ELN with an appropriate data export function can facilitate building rapidly accessible/searchable digital archive
Using notebook in a controlled environment (e.g. cleanrooms, containment laboratories)	Specialist notebooks may be required, notebook must remain within laboratory	ELN can provide seamless access inside and outside of controlled environment, assuming suitable access devices provided
Interoperating with other laboratory systems (e.g. measurement /inventory/procurement databases)	Manual static reference	Possibility to incorporate automated/direct links using persistent identifiers and APIs, dependent on ELN support
Sharing entries as open research data/open science	Time intensive as per other sharing issues	Built-in support with some ELNs
Maintaining a legal record	Facilitated by signing and co-signing notebook pages, plus secure storage of notebook	Facilitated by digital signatures/timestamping and robust backup regime

Table 1: Different laboratory notebook interactions, comparing their ease between paper and electronic media.

Figure 2: Simplified illustration of a commonly used ELN architecture. Users interact with the ELN software via workstations and/or mobile devices, with off-premises access possible via technologies such as virtual private networks or by exposing the ELN to the wider internet. The ELN software, database and file storage may coexist on the same physical server or operate on separate hardware. The server may be run as a local installation at an institution, or as part of a cloud-hosted product from the software vendor. Additional requirements include a backup server, which should be geographically separate from the ELN (and should consist of multiple layers of redundancy). Third-party services include access to single sign-on servers (to facilitate a better user experience), trusted timestamping authorities (for independently digitally signing notebook entries), or other laboratory systems (such as inventory management, etc).

An electronic laboratory notebook is typically a combination of user-interface, centralised database and file store

Figure 2 illustrates a simplified view of a commonly adopted ELN architecture.^{10,12,26,27} Notebook entries may be stored in a relational database with attached files in a file store. The ELN software facilitates user access and defines how notebook entries can be accessed and written. The software may be accessed via a web browser or in some cases through a custom application written for a specific platform (e.g. desktop or mobile operating system apps). Application-based ELNs may cause compatibility issues in academic research environments that typically feature a diverse range of operating systems.²⁸ Depending on the implementation, the separate ELN components may be separate servers,²⁷ in different physical locations. This major conceptual shift from paper notebooks brings both opportunities and challenges. While the underlying technology is ideally invisible to the end user, the choice of ELN can influence the availability of different features. For example, most ELNs are ill-suited to storing large volumes of raw data (either from a performance or cost perspective). A locally-hosted ELN server may rapidly run out of physical storage space. A cloud-hosted server may quickly incur significant hosting costs as storage and bandwidth requirements increase.

Sensitive data, for example patient or commercially-sensitive information, may fall under local institution or legally-mandated data protection regulations, for example GDPR 2016/679,²⁹ which dictates the handling and safeguarding of personal data within the European Union. This may restrict the physical location and transfer of data, excluding the use of off-premises ELNs that use internationally-based cloud-based infrastructure.³⁰ Locally-hosted ELNs may provide greater control over data security by restricting notebook access to users inside an institutional network (i.e. access devices must be physically on premises or connected remotely via technologies such as Virtual Private Networks).

The ability to create immutable notebook entries which cannot be removed or altered after creation is critical for academic and legal integrity. Paper notebooks implement this typically through rules and procedures, for example, by prohibiting the removal of notebook pages, and signing and counter-signing notebook entries. Not all ELNs address this issue, again precluding the use of some products. For example, general note-taking software packages, such as Microsoft OneNote and Evernote, do not typically include features to digitally sign or timestamp entries, with inefficient workarounds such as signing exported files required.²⁸ The level of verification required depends on both regulation requirements and locally accepted laboratory notebook standards. For example, it may be sufficient to rely upon administrator-defined software features, such as the ability of a supervisor to lock notebook entries to prevent them from being edited or to disable entry deletion.

If verifying the provenance of notebook entries is critical, the ELN should incorporate technologies that adhere to recognised standards for trusted timestamping, such as RFC 3161,³¹ or ANSI X9.95-2016.³² Trusted timestamping uses an audited third-party organisation (typically a commercial provider), to digitally sign and timestamp a file. A hashing algorithm is applied to a digital file, for example a pdf file that corresponds to a notebook entry. A hash file (a small, mathematically unique representation of the file) is generated. A hash file cannot be reverse engineered to recreate the original data so can be safely transmitted to the trusted timestamping authority via the internet. The authority digitally signs and timestamps the hash, in the process generating a third file (a token). This token is sent back to the ELN software and stored alongside the original file. Any modifications to the original file will invalidate the token, as recalculating the hash of the modified file will result in one different to the digitally signed value contained within the token. The process allows a digital file's integrity to be verified at a given point in time. Although technically complex, this process is typically performed invisibly to the user.

While trusted timestamping incorporates the concept of digital signatures, it adds the additional benefit of not only verifying the sender's identity, but also the time at which an entry was timestamped. In practical terms, local policy is required to ensure users routinely timestamp their notebook entries, as the date and time of timestamping is being recorded, not the instant an experiment was conducted. Procedures for archiving data should ensure both the timestamped file and timestamp token are properly preserved.

Open-source and commercial electronic laboratory notebooks have different costs and benefits

In our survey, commercial ELNs were observed to be far more prevalent than open-source ELNs (147 vs 24 products identified). **Table 2** compares commercial to open-source approaches. While SaaS is a widely adopted licensing model (for example, institutional subscriptions to Microsoft Office 365 or Google Workspace), SaaS ELNs may be prohibitively expensive for individual research groups due to per-user pricing, ever-growing file storage costs, and an indefinite subscription required to maintain access. In 2017, Kanza et al. reported that in a survey of 169 users participating in an ELN pilot study both limited financial budgets and the time required to implement an ELN were both major concerns.¹⁵ Similarly, while open-source ELNs can have relatively low initial and ongoing financial costs, they require time to run and maintain, and may require server hardware to be purchased. The relatively modest requirements for many open-source ELNs make it feasible to re-provision old computing hardware to act as an ELN server, helping to reduce this cost. Costs can scale with the size of deployment, for example commercial site-wide licenses may be negotiated at preferential rates than the per-user pricing available to individual research groups.³³ Implementing an open-source ELN at institutional scale can take advantage of pre-existing server infrastructure and ICT support. Some commercial providers offer free or reduced pricing for academic users.¹⁵

Open-source ELNs have the benefit of allowing not only the data to be archived, but also the underlying software itself. Technologies such as virtualisation present a feasible pathway to preserve the operating environment of the ELN for future access, beyond software and hardware obsolescence. The open codebase also means data formats and standards are fully exposed, facilitating the future development of tools to reparse or extract data. When assessing an ELN hosted by a third-party, consider what will happen to notebook entries when the product is discontinued. Some open-source projects (such as the Open Science Framework)³⁴ may include contingency plans and funds to ensure the ongoing preservation of research data. If an ELN provides data export functions, these should be tested to confirm they provide the required level of functionality.

Feature	Open source	Commercial
Ease of deployment	Requires client to have knowledge and/or hardware to implement	Available 'out-of-the box'
Support available	Online contributor community / may or may not have limited developer support	Company dependent, may offer training sessions, webinars, etc
Data backup	Self-arranged – flexible and full control	Either automatic by the vendor (e.g. automated cloud-based backups) or self-arranged
Initial costs	<p>No software cost</p> <p>Server hardware costs (and/or private cloud-server rental)</p> <p>Provision of access devices to users</p> <p>Time cost to setup and integrate with existing institutional facilities</p> <p>Time cost for user training and migration</p>	<p>No server hardware cost (if cloud hosted by supplier)</p> <p>No, or small, initial software cost</p> <p>Provision of access devices to users</p> <p>Time cost for user training and migration</p>
Ongoing costs	<p>No ongoing subscription cost</p> <p>No additional cost per additional user (assuming available server capacity)</p> <p>Periodic hardware maintenance cost (e.g. replacing servers, or increasing storage capacity)</p> <p>Time cost for regular system maintenance</p> <p>If using a private cloud-server, ongoing rental cost)</p> <p>Time cost for training each additional new user</p>	<p>Ongoing subscription fees per month/annum and/or per user</p> <p>Typically each additional user increases costs</p> <p>Increasing user data may result in additional subscription costs</p> <p>No ongoing hardware/maintenance costs</p> <p>Time cost for training each additional new user</p>

Ongoing development	<p>Reliant on open-source community to continue to maintain software (e.g. issuing patches for security vulnerabilities, or development of new features)</p> <p>Users can directly suggest and implement new features</p>	<p>Software updates (security, new features) normally provided as part of subscription</p> <p>New feature development dependent upon company priorities</p>
Software security	Public codebase allows interrogation from many parties, quickly identifying security issues	Private codebase limits scope for checking for security issues, reliant on the company to quickly implement fixes
Outboarding strategy	<p>Free access to all notebook entries and files</p> <p>Either export feature incorporated or can create custom methods for extracting data</p>	<p>Reliant on software to provide appropriate export solutions – some may restrict file formats or the preservation of certain features or elements, leading to risk of data lock-in</p> <p>If company fails, risk of data becoming trapped/inaccessible on company servers</p>
Data storage	Complete control over location and accessibility of stored data	Product-dependent, some may offer compliance with specific regulations

Table 2: Comparison of ELN features for open source and commercial solutions. Note: this is a generalised comparison – not all ELN products offer the same levels of functionality.

Electronic laboratory notebooks are not a solution to poor data management

ELNs do not resolve the challenge of systematically storing raw data and are just one part of a holistic data management strategy. Successfully implementing an ELN requires reflection on current practice to determine how a laboratory handles and stores information.^{35,36} As with paper notebooks, policy, training and enforcement are required to ensure users record timely, useful and complete lab entries. New users require training to understand the purpose and expectations of laboratory notebook use within a given organisation. A policy for how, when and by whom notebooks are monitored sets expectations. An offboarding procedure should be implemented to ensure outgoing user data is appropriately archived.

Procedures for linking raw data, laboratory notebook entries, analysed data, and publication data should be clearly defined and enforced. Data may be stored on a user's local computer, centralised group or measurement-specific servers, or publicly-available repositories. Persistent identifiers such as digital object identifiers (DOIs) can be used to help link resources, with ELN entries acting as centralised documents that connect to multiple files and data.³⁵ Some ELNs already generate unique identifiers for each notebook entry.¹² To help verify the integrity of externally stored data, ELNs can be used to record cryptographic hashes of files.

Some ELNs feature application programming interfaces (APIs) that allow other software to directly read and write notebook entries.¹² For example, a user conducting a computer-controlled experiment could allow that equipment to directly record experimental or process details, potentially streamlining routine measurements, assuming support for the API exists. Laboratories with well-defined workflows, such as electron microscopy,³⁷ or genetic analysis,²⁷ may benefit from specialised ELNs that incorporate notebook entries within the data capture workflow, or have been designed with equipment integration as a primary goal.

Successful ELNs recognise the needs of their users

Within an academic research environment both time and money are at a premium. Ideally, if adopted, ELNs for the academic research laboratory should be implemented at institutional level, harnessing existing ICT infrastructure, and with a sufficient commitment for ongoing support to encourage uptake.³⁸ While a handful of university-based surveys and studies of ELN implementation exist,^{15,38,39} the reported level of success varies, suggesting careful user-engagement, product choice and support is key to successful deployment.

Critically, the implementation of an ELN should not introduce a net burden to the user. If users are unable or unwilling to use the time-saving features of ELNs, it may ultimately be a hindrance. For example, for a researcher who regularly draws chemical structures or writes equations into their notebook, most non-specialist ELNs will be less convenient than paper,³⁸ and the introduction of an ELN may be perceived as undesirable.¹⁸ Lack of support for systems such as LaTeX can be a barrier to adoption in specific disciplines.⁴⁰

Internal trialling of a small number of products; jointly agreed compromises or incorporating integrations to specialist solutions may be required, such as ELNs capable of handling chemical structures.⁴¹ Simple infrastructure factors, such as an absence of reliable WiFi,^{6,15,25} insufficient benchspace to place a laptop computer,¹⁵ or lack of access to up-to-date hardware and software in the laboratory can also adversely affect users.³⁸ The prevalent culture of private and personal academic laboratory notebooks should be recognised, with one ELN study noting that researchers felt embarrassed when required to share their notebook with colleagues.⁴²

User training should be recognised as an additional time burden, with researchers already expected to master a wide range of software packages.⁴³ Similarly, many laboratories already use laboratory information management systems (LIMS) for inventory handling, equipment booking, and procurement. Introducing a further standalone system can work against the time-benefits of digitisation and integration.⁴⁴ Implementing an ELN is an opportunity to reflect upon and consolidate existing practice, with many ELNs incorporating LIMS-style components.

ELNs are an opportunity to consider the broader philosophy of academic laboratory research

With care, ELNs can be used to support information capture, making it more consistent, accessible and usable to both current and future generations of scientists. Some ELNs cater to aspects of open science,^{45,46} allowing them to be configured to share data outside of organisations, supporting initiatives such as the FAIR Data Principles (a proposal that scientific data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).⁴⁷

The abstraction of the notebook storage infrastructure away from the user enables ELN architectures different to that illustrated in **Figure 2** to be adopted. Rather than using a private database of notebook entries, an ELN could implement a publicly distributed decentralised record store (using technologies such as blockchain).⁴⁸ While a potential mechanism to enable open science, the technology is distinct, as it could similarly be used to create a record of research provenance (i.e. through hashed/encrypted approaches similar to timestamping) rather than entire notebook entries.

ELNs might be integrated with computational semantic technologies,¹⁸ which allow the meaning of human language to be automatically inferred. This would allow research metadata to be automatically derived, aiding search efforts; or create automated insights by linking relevant data together.⁴⁴ Similarly, while research data management remains an open challenge, the integration of ELNs with institutional repositories may offer new opportunities to simplify and improve this process.⁴⁹

In summary, for researchers and institutions considering implementing an ELN, a nuanced understanding of laboratory culture is needed to facilitate a respectful and ultimately user-supported deployment. The barriers to entry must be carefully managed as these have the potential to create technological divides within the academic community, diluting the benefits of ELNs. With careful consideration, successful implementation of an ELN presents a pathway to greater knowledge development and transfer within academic research.

Supporting Information

Supplementary Information contains more detailed information on the ELN product survey methodology. Raw survey data and analysis code can be found here: [https://dx.doi.org/\[DOI_TBC\]](https://dx.doi.org/[DOI_TBC]).

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Author contributions

S.G.H. and A.N.V. wrote the manuscript. M.M.S. supervised the work and edited the manuscript.

Competing interests

S.G.H. and A.N.V. are the Systems Administrators for Stevens Group ELN, with uses the open-source software package eLabFTW. S.G.H. has provided feedback via public forums to the developer of eLabFTW.

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